

Humanity and the Impact of History in Anthropology

The Interconnectedness of History and Anthropology, and Its Role in Colonization.

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Abstract

This dissertation brings to revision very classical anthropological debates around history, agency, and representation of societies, and is for the establishment of a reflexive relationship between archivists, museums, and the culture of fieldwork. Taking into consideration the themes of colonization, representation, and politics of knowledge, illuminated by insights originating from a study of the Peabody Museum, the dissertation engages critically with what narrations are retained and by what means this is done. It proposes a methodological framework combining historical anthropology articulated with modern critical theorists in order to investigate the manner in which societies represent acts of themselves and how scholars may be ethically engaged in such a process. The article sets forth a set of guiding questions to encourage process approaches from a decolonial and collaborative perspective and further proceeds to argue for plurality, responsibility, and co-creative meanings.

Introduction

Would Anthropology even exist if Europe hadn't colonized part of the world? To answer that question, it's necessary to look to History itself, analyzing the evolution of humanity and how we wrote and kept records of it. To understand history is the first step in comprehending anthropology as a discipline, to understand the way it appeared, and how society first applied, and what we expected out of that.

To study history is to understand how human society writes its own actions and consequences. To study anthropology is to understand which society and why they took those actions, and their implications collectively. It is extremely important to highlight concepts that will be framing this research, from how society was built, to what is in fact history, and to what extent different humans have different cultures, which shape differently their own history. It may be observed that if not through colonization, there wouldn't be slavery, and even other races wouldn't be considered different, and only versions of oneself, increasing the tolerance and respect of humanity.

To research the conditions in which Anthropology existed, and how it correlated to history itself, field research was done on the Peabody Museum of Archaeology & Ethnology at Harvard University, in Cambridge, Massachusetts, United States. The exhibitions visited were: "All The World is Here", "Encounters in the Americas", "Hall of the North American Indian", and "Muchos Méxicos". Those exhibits were chosen to take a closer look at the history told of colonized people, as well as the history of Anthropology itself.

In addition to this field research, an interview was conducted with a Historian, Ligia Fornazieri, Master of Social History by Unicamp in Brazil. The focus was on understanding History as a discipline and as a movement, and how it impacted and was impacted by human behavior, and eventually the rise of Anthropology. The initial topic was to ask the question, "Would anthropology exist without history?". As well as to get a in depth perspective from a historian, several authors were observed as part of the research, as Franz Boas, Ruth Benedict, Edward Said, and Eric Hobsbawm, authors which own writings gave enough material and resources to better position and comprehend the disciplines, defining anthropology, bringing notions of culture and concepts build by occident, as well as reviewing history and its development.

Opening with History

“All human beings are conscious of the past (...) by virtue of living with people older than themselves.” In this statement, Eric Hobsbawm, European historian, makes it clear that people become aware of the past by sharing it with others, passing down events that took place at a different time than the one they currently share with younger generations. Similarly, future generations will only be aware of the past by living with the older generation, and eventually learn and hear from the past. Past that is, according to Hobsbawm, defined as *“clearly is and must be a particular selection from the infinity of what is remembered or capable of being remembered.”*

It is part of human nature to gather, and in this gathering, there's sharing. To share makes us more human, learning the same behavior that previous generations have learned, to survive initially and essentially. One important aspect to learn is to share what specific actions have brought specific consequences, and by doing so, one builds new behavior, by example and reference.

One thing is clear: humans have always been telling stories, and those stories have become history. *“Ever since humans are humans, they've talked about their history. It's part of human formation. There's clear growth and learning as history is told.”* – According to Ligia – *“This is inherent to human and social behavior. A clear example is how Greeks wrote about the Iliad, about Troy, to teach and learn about mistakes.”*

More important than defining what history is, is to define what history is to humans and their societies, and what anthropology is to history? History can be seen as a tool we have been using not simply to keep records as a huge catalog folder of events, but to learn from specific people, in specific times, that in the collective mind of a civilization is worth telling, to be either avoided, or repeated. History can be used to shape the future, depending on who tells and who listens.

Is to Colonize to Survive?

The reason why it is so important to understand history itself is to guard it properly in its place, removing the judgment of morality from it. One clear example is how history tells, and to some extent, accepts colonization as part of the evolution and development of human society. When there's colonization, there's not simply a war; there's dominance, there's appropriation, there's imposition. To colonize is to explore and exploit, removing others' own behaviors and history, in the benefit of one's own.

History tells of different civilizations that are far older than European society, which have had a series of advances in navigation, exploration, and societal development, although they have not executed colonization. *"The idea of colonization is European. Indigenous people didn't have that interest, and Asian societies didn't have the same notion of colonization. It's part of the occidental civilization, the idea of dominating and forcing its culture on others"*, according to Ligia in an interview. Could we conceive a world in which another civilization was a heavy colonizer, reshaping history and eventually anthropology?

If we look at Egypt, whose world-historical importance would take place, its own destiny was to be annexed to Europe, preferably, as described by Edward Said in his book *Orientalism*. This example not only shows the colonizing nature of Europe, but also the way Western history mainly tells this event. Egypt could as well have been able to conquer and colonize other lands and continents as much as the Ancient European people. The fact that they haven't shows that it was not part of their nature to do so. We see instead how Europe colonized it and often exhibits Egyptian artifacts, not as part of what they consider ordinary, but rather peculiar and exotic.

Looking specifically to the colonization of the Americas, we face a similar scenario, where history shows, relatively advanced societies across what we now call Mesoamerica, that haven't taken part in colonizing other people. Those societies had their own systems and customs, seen as extremely different and unusual by Europeans when the Spaniards arrived to conquer, in search of wealth. There are cases in which the mission was to educate and to present religion properly, showing the assumed correct god, all in European terms. There was no colonizing on the colonized terms.

Anthropology as Instrument

While History is inherent to human beings, as a need to understand themselves as individuals, Anthropology is the discipline that studies others and not oneself. It is important, though, to understand the terms in which Anthropology surfaced, with its origin in Europe. As defended by Franz Boas, in opposition to the idea that Anthropology is *“often depicted as a collection of curious facts, telling about the peculiar appearance of exotic people and describing their strange customs and beliefs.”* And instead, it is *“...a clear understanding of the principles of anthropology illuminates the social process of our own times and may show us, (...), what to do and what to avoid.”* We bring it closer to how Anthropology is used, in addition to history, to teach about people and behaviors. The question is, which ones, and to teach what?

Although Boas, quite relevantly, ponders on the Anthropology's definition, it is important to acknowledge and consider the aspects in which anthropology as a discipline took into consideration the one and the others as subjects of study. If we understand anthropology as the study of others, it might as well be considered that the reason on why the study of others became significant was because there was another, in opposition to one. The only way to recognize the existence of others is to get introduced to them. The interest of exploration was not to replicate, for instance others' learnings, but to enforce their own.

Ligia also stated that *“Anthropology served as an instrument of colonization. Colonizers saw native and different people and cultures, judged them as savages, and not civilized, according to their patterns of civilizations. In that context, anthropology might be understood as a civilizing character.”* What was considered civilized was only the European standards, with everything else, religiously, customary, appearance-wise, described as uncivilized people.

Colonialism was, in the name of bringing civilization and progress, to impose European culture on those different people. It might be as well considered that anthropology was used to separate what was not equal, was not organized the same as European society was organized, and a means to understand the differences, and not look for similarities. Putting societies as others was a way also to justify doing to them, and to treat them not in the same way they would treat themselves. Finding means to justify their ends, and to outline institutionally the need for colonization. Nationalism is a concept that draws this line, and clearly puts people into different groups, by their linguistic and cultural characteristics, building the concept of differentiation, not only by the place they are born, but also by their customs and behavior.

Not Everything is Lost

Through those lenses, one may consider that Anthropology to a certain extent, more than a discipline to help one to understand others, to learn and grow, was the subtle way in which Europe could purposefully and peacefully present how exotic and peculiar other societies were, and why they needed the European advances, while making sure to collect whatever they were in need now. There's no such thing as colonization from another perspective, unless you're from Europe. They've institutionalized and made it a lifestyle, searching in other places and people, for products and prizes.

What's left then is the alternative of looking to the results of history as it was and how anthropology has also constantly evolved with history. History for the sake of history doesn't exist. If humans don't act, don't change the status quo, there's no history. There wouldn't be different times, conditions, and circumstances. Humans act instinctively, to survive, and to give continuity to their own species. Although, as rational beings, we transform that into living, and leave a legacy, not only to exist, but to coexist and to build history. Ironically, coexist only among those considered similar and equals, with the same characteristics, same culture, and behavior.

Humans build their history through actions and consequences. Those are a reflex of their existence and their culture, as described by Ruth Benedict; *"From the moment of his birth, the customs into which he is born shape his experience and behaviour. By the time he can talk, he is a little creature of his culture...."* The very aspects that build one's society culture are the aspects that drive historical changes. Big historical moments happen in the change of behavior, that change is motivated by people that being part of their own culture, or an outsider, looks at that and doesn't agree, not acknowledging the prevalent culture they want to see in the future.

Those historical changes eventually change the way we perceive the past, building an intense, gigantic, and incredible circle that constantly spins and gives new perspective. Is that notion that Putnam and Boas' vision on anthropology gives fuel, in a way that the discipline is not used to justify changes to another culture, but yes, to acknowledge the existence, and recognize the acceptance of innumerable customs, that were as written in history, seen as uncivilized, intolerable, and needed to be changed. The approach to which anthropology is then positioned, as a way to not justify previous behaviors, now understood to be inadequate, is a lighthouse to guide the decolonization much needed in the world's societies.

Conclusion

It is difficult to respond to how something would unfold if it hadn't been unfolded as it was. It's a journey through a sea of realities and parallel alternatives that cannot exist in our reality. Each factor, when looked at individually to study its impact, cannot be removed to the circumstances in which those happened. It is possible to imagine adjusting and shaping reality based on other possible outcomes, through different alternatives than the one known, to see if in fact, there's something potentially better out there.

On History itself, it's hard to remove humans from history and history from them. The count of time, brought systematically by different people, is human. Nature doesn't count time or track history. They act by instinct and follow the direct impact of effects caused by time, such as seasons, and the very day and night effects by the orbit of Earth. The chronological recording of facts and events is how humanity builds its history, filling it with stories that they intrinsically share collectively. Would history be any different if human interest in other humans didn't exist? Is that interest truly about another human being, or about themselves? If telling our history shapes our behavior, what is our behavior if not the pure manifestation of reproducing similar or different actions, looking for the same or distinguished consequences? Would that be the very base on which Anthropology exists?

Against all odds, anthropology finds its way, with an interesting perspective of understanding the other, quite differently than simply observing exotic and peculiar differences. Now it is a tool we can use to see not only why different people have different behaviors, but also, why they have similar ones, and if it really matters though. Why do humans want to study and understand the collective behavior of others who are different than themselves? Is it a search for justification for their actions? Is it an assurance of their own beliefs? It is hard not to see anthropology as this described civilizing tool, used by colonizers to justify their own actions in changing other societies' behaviors, and unfortunately even deleting their culture in the name of a claimed civilized development. Ironically, we now use history and its sanctuaries, so-called museums, to guard the remnants of unchangeable past, and inexistent reality, and future to former civilizations, civilized in their own ways.

In retrospect, would anthropology exist if Europe hadn't colonized most nations of the world? In fact, it might not even exist. Europeans wouldn't look to native Americans, indigenous, Aztecs, Mayans, for example and judge what they named exotic and peculiar, wanting to change those. There wouldn't be this relative interest and need to begin studying these different behaviors if there wasn't also this interest in eventually restructuring and judging those. People

would be simply people, with different customs, norms, and organization, according to what their own history taught them, based on their own locales, geographies, climate, and environment. All those aspects shape our behavior as well, as much as history.

In conclusion, the outcome should always be aimed to be positive, and in understanding the reasons and motivations, we can look to history and apply the same rules of judgement, choosing to shape reality as much as possible in the pro of humanity. Now the challenge is to look to Anthropology and to History, making sure to learn from the past, aiming for a better future, filled with not trying to understand different people and different cultures, but to acknowledge and accept, learning from different stories as well. The question is, regardless of how Anthropology surfaced, is it being used properly?

Methods

The Ethnographic methods used as part of this research were Interview, Observation, and Archival Research. The interview was conducted with a master's degree in history, and besides books and authors researched, material from the ethnology museum was observed.

The research surfaced as an interesting point, since, as an immigrant from a colonized country by Europe, constantly reminded of what if, and how our own history, culture, families, lands, and people would be if there wasn't the systemic colonization by Europe.

As a Brazilian born, I have attachments with the country and often wonder what my country would have been if not colonized and explored as it was. How would indigenous people be? Eventually, the same as the ones that still have no contact with other people. Would Mesoamerican civilizations rather merge?

In addition, the scenario is quite curious, as per ethnicity results from my DNA, shows 0% Native Brazilian Indigenous, and 72% European. My family migrated from Europe to a colonized country. Would that even happen if Brazil weren't colonized? There's an obvious interest and relation in how I see myself in that tapestry of history and culture, and studying myself and my history, I can aim to bring more sense to the collective history and anthropology.

Photographs and Screenshots

1)

ENCOUNTERS WITH THE AMERICAS

Before 1492 the Americas were not isolated. Arctic peoples easily moved between continents. Norse sailors reached North America and, around AD 1000, established a temporary settlement. But such contacts did not fundamentally change European, American, or Asian cultures.

By 1000 BC, independent Native American civilizations developed in Central Mexico and South America. Central Americans used the concept of zero in mathematical calculations by the first century BC. The Maya kept astronomical records as precise as any in the world. Classic Maya city states of Mexico and Guatemala were equal in size to those of classical Greece.

These and later Native American civilizations, however, were very different from European, Asian, and African civilizations. They relied on stone tools for construction and human labor for transport. Pottery was made without glazes or the wheel. Metal was used primarily in costume. The Aztec warriors who resisted the armies of Cortés in 1521 were armed with wooden clubs set with sharp glass blades that shattered against the guns and metal swords of the Europeans.

After 1492 European governments tried to impose new religious and social practices on the native cultures of the Americas. But even when a measure of European control was established, resistance continued. Periodic military rebellions often followed native prophecies. People were forced to adopt European practices but used them in ways that preserved their own values. By 1600, disease, warfare, and forced labor reduced native population of the Americas by as much as ninety percent. Yet those who lived passed on to their descendants a vital sense of cultural identity. Today, many native peoples use distinctive costume, language, religion, and social customs as weapons in their struggle for cultural survival.

Classic Maya glyph that was used to begin dates in the native calendar

Five centuries of encounters between the native peoples of the Americas and newer arrivals from Europe, Africa, and Asia have forged a complex cultural mosaic in this hemisphere. European colonization of the Americas in the sixteenth century began a global transformation. As people moved, they brought new ideas as well as animals, plants, gold, silver, and other resources from continent to continent.

Almost a quarter million Spanish and Portuguese immigrants resettled in Central and South America and the West Indies by 1600. These Europeans also carried diseases unknown in the Americas, and even before colonies were established, millions of people died from their effects. It is estimated that smallpox alone killed over one quarter of the native population of Latin America between 1520 and 1584.

To meet their demands for labor, too great to be satisfied by the reduced native populations, sixteenth-century European colonists introduced slavery. Beginning as early as 1505, Africans were torn from their homes and brought to the Americas in numbers equal to or greater than European immigration. Despite the horrifying loss of their own population, native peoples of the Americas survived. Today, their descendants work to maintain their distinctive cultural identities and control their futures.

Mary Magdalene, weaving the traditional woman's costume of the Maya town of Magdalenas

Aztecs defend Tenochtitlan against Spanish and their native allies, AD 1519. Drawing from the Lienzo de Tlaxcala.

Exhibit "Encounters in the Americas" at the Peabody Museum.

Mesoamerican societies were perceived as uncivilized by Europeans.

2)

The Mesoamerican World

In the area of modern Mexico and Guatemala which anthropologists today call Mesoamerica, sixteenth-century Spanish adventurers encountered highly complex societies. Including the Formative period Olmec, Classic period Maya, and Postclassic period Aztec and Maya, Mesoamerican cultures shared a set of values and a common history reflected at all levels, from daily meals to poetic speech. Mesoamerican values survive today in transformed fashion in the cultures of descendants of the sixteenth-century native peoples.

Mesoamericans believed in a multi-layered universe with systems of the supernatural. Gods and their powers were everywhere. Source: J. P. Hensler, *Cosmology and the Classic Period*

Mesoamerican peoples relied on agriculture for survival, growing corn, beans, and squash on family lands. They conceived of the world as a layered place, divided in four directions by the path of the sun from east to west, from the height of the sky to the depths of the underworld. Mesoamericans used elaborate calendars to time the movement of the stars, set dates for ceremonies, and determine the fate of individuals. Mesoamerican religions related the survival of the people to their dealings with the supernatural world, home to their ancestors and powerful spirits. In their temples, ballcourts, and public plazas, Mesoamerican people practiced rituals which gave meaning to their existence. In these rituals, a small ruling class played a crucial role as intermediaries

between the people and the supernatural world.

The shared values of Mesoamerican peoples arose through a long history of strong connections, cemented by exchange of useful plants, material for stone tools, and ideas. Distinct Mesoamerican languages share a rich heritage of poetic language. In figures of speech, Mesoamerican peoples expressed concepts we can also see carved in stone and modeled in pottery. Houses are presented as animate beings whose doors are mouths, and people are linked by kinship as if by a rope. These images and their settings within archaeological sites provide a window into a world brought into abrupt confrontation with European society in the sixteenth century.

Some houses, under stone of Maya people, represent the open mouth of a supernatural being.
Source: J. Hensler, *Mesoamerica: Life Before the Conquest*

Exhibit "Encounters in the Americas" at the Peabody Museum.

Mesoamerican societies' culture, confronted by Europe.

3)

Detalle del Bordado de una Anquera Mexicana del siglo XVIII
Embroidery Detail from 18th Century Mexican Anquera

Un Choque de Culturas
Cuando Hernán Cortés y su ejército invasor recorrieron la costa oriental de México, se encontraron con una sociedad rebotante de actividad económica, diversidad cultural y una intrincada jerarquía social. Durante miles de años, antes de la introducción forzada de los modos de vida europeos, los pueblos de Mesoamérica habían inventado sus propias formas de agricultura, gobierno, religión, arquitectura, escritura, astronomía y matemáticas. En el corazón de este rico entorno cultural se encontraba el lugar que hoy llamamos México.

A Collision of Cultures
As Hernán Cortés and his invading army traveled along Mexico's eastern shore, they encountered a society bustling with economic activity, cultural diversity and an intricate social hierarchy. For thousands of years before the forced introduction of European ways of life, the peoples of Mesoamerica had invented their own forms of agriculture, government, religion, architecture, writing, astronomy, and mathematics. At the heart of this rich cultural milieu was the place we now call Mexico.

Fusión para Crear Algo Nuevo
Los españoles trajeron consigo nuevas prácticas culturales y habitantes, procedentes de Europa, África y otras partes del mundo. Incluso frente a los agresivos intentos de asimilación, las visiones del mundo y las formas de vida de los pueblos indígenas persistieron, mezclándose con las de sus opresores y transformándose. De esta fusión cultural surgieron nuevas prácticas religiosas, vestimenta, arte, música e incluso formas de comer; en conjunto, han llegado a definir la diversidad cultural y el carácter del México contemporáneo.

Merging to Create Something New
The Spanish brought with them new cultural practices and peoples from Europe, Africa and other parts of the wider world. Even in the face of aggressive attempts at assimilation, the worldviews and ways of life of indigenous peoples persisted, intermingling with those of their oppressors and transforming both. Out of this cultural fusion emerged new religious practices, dress, art, music, even ways of eating. Together, they have come to define the cultural diversity and character of contemporary Mexico.

LIBRACIÓN DE LOS OBJETOS EN ESTA EXPOSICIÓN
LOCATIONS OF OBJECTS IN THIS EXHIBIT

- Oaxaca: Mexico City, San Bartolomé, San Felipe, San Juan, San Marcos, San Mateo
- Michoacán de Ocampo: La Paz, San Juan
- Hidalgo: Toluca, Mexico City
- Querétaro: La Paz, San Juan
- Coahuila de Zaragoza: Saltillo

Exhibit “Muchos Méxicos” at the Peabody Museum.
An example of Spanish culture imposing on Mexico.

5)

World map showing Colonialism from 1492 to 2008
Presents a very short history of colonialism.

6)

Countries that have been under European control

- Europe
- Colonized or controlled by Europe
- Partial European control or influence
- European sphere of influence
- Never colonized by Europe

A map showing that basically every nation was under European colonization.

7)

General Information STAAC Production Events

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Spanish: Comprehends Reasonably, Speaks Little, Reads Well, Writes Little.

Scientific, Technological, Artistic and Cultural Production

Bibliographical Production

Presentations of Work

1. FORNAZIERI, L. L. O poder normativo no projeto de Justiça do Trabalho (1938-1938). 2014. (Presentation/Communication).

Events

Participation in events

1. Curso de Introdução à História Pública. 2011. (Participation In Event/Other).
2. Lei em mudança: Trabalhadores e Legislação antes da CLT (1937-1943). 2010. (Participation In Event/Congress).
3. Seminário Internacional Anísio Edgar Lourenço: História e Pesquisa. 2010. (Participation In Event/Seminary).

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Citation & Bibliography

Benedict, Ruth. Patterns of Culture. Boston, First Mariner Books, 1934

Said, Edward. Orientalism. New York, Vintage Books, 1978

Bloch, Marc. The Historian's Craft. New York, Vintage Books, 1953

Boas, Franz. Anthropology & Modern Life. New Brunswick, Transactional Publishers, 1932

Young, Paul. Postcolonialism: A Very Short Introduction. Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2003

Hobsbawm, Eric. On History. New York, The New Press, 1997

The School District of Philadelphia:

<https://www.philasd.org/curriculum/wp-content/uploads/sites/825/2020/03/WorldSS.pdf>

Vox: 500 years of European colonialism, in one animated map:

<https://www.vox.com/2014/5/8/5691954/colonialism-collapse-gif-imperialism>

Brilliant Maps: Short History of Colonialism Since 1492 In One GIF:

<https://brilliantmaps.com/colonialism-history/>